

PERFORATION OF COMPACTED SINTERED ALUMINIUM POWDER (CSAP) TARGETS REINFORCED WITH CARBON AND GLASS FIBERS

Gholamhossien Liaghat
Mechanical Engineering Department
Tarbiat Modarres University, P.O.Box 14155-4838, Tehran, Iran

ABSTRACT

In this investigation the effectiveness of targets made of composites based on compacted sintered aluminium powder (CSAP) as the matrix body plus either a layer of carbon or glass fibre reinforcement at the middle of it was investigated.

Detailed experimental work was performed in perforation of targets made from CSAP having different volume percentages of either glass or carbon fibres mixed either with the metal powder or placed in the form of layers inside the powder which were then compacted and sintered. These targets were then perforated by bullets fired at almost the same impact velocity and their ballistic resistance were compared by measuring the residual velocity of the bullets.

In this paper the results of the above observations are presented and a comprehensive discussion of results are given.

INTRODUCTION

The design and construction of a single layer target system to withstand ballistic impact and to resist perforation due to the projectiles of varying shapes and sizes when the total weight of the system has to be considered entail the following[1] :

(a) the maximum possible thickness; (b) high bulk and shear moduli; (c) high yield stress to maintain the resistance to deformation at high stress levels; and, (d) high resistance to fracture when large tensile stresses occur.

No one target material maximizes all of the above properties when the total areal density of the target must be minimized. This has led to the development of composite targets where a high strength material is backed by a material that can resist failure due to the tensile stress.

Several low density but high strength materials, especially in compression, such as ceramics, can satisfy the first three of the aforementioned requirements, but not the fourth because they are very weak in tension. To satisfy the fourth requirement a composite target consisting of ceramic as frontal layer and another material such as

aluminium in the back has been considered.

Ceramic armour is a composite material consisting of a ceramic layer in front where the projectile first impacts. The ceramic material, being at the front face, destroys the projectile which then disintegrates, its kinetic energy being dissipated as heat and in the generation of fracture surfaces in the ceramic. The backing material is usually selected on the basis of its rigidity. The greater the rigidity of the backing material the higher is the stopping power of the ceramic plate. The backing material is normally made from a material reinforced either with glass or carbon fibre or from other laminated material such as Kevlar. This traps the fragments of both the projectile and of the ceramic plate[2].

The present materials that have been used so far and act either as cover or for matrix purposes, are either polymers or plastics which hold both the front and the back, i.e. the ceramic and the backing layers together.

The object of the present investigation, however, was to study the effectiveness of targets made of composites based on compacted sintered aluminium powder (CSAP) as the matrix body to hold a layer or layers of ceramic plus either a layer of carbon or glass fibre reinforcement at the middle of it.

MATERIALS, EQUIPMENT AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

MATERIALS FOR COMPOSITE TARGETS

Powder Metal Used As Matrix For Composite

The atomized (100 mesh) aluminium powder, supplied by Metal Powder Ltd, Birmingham, was used for making the matrix of the composite target specimens.

Reinforcement Fibres

Two kinds of fibres were used in the present investigation: (i) carbon fibres, (ii) glass fibres. These fibres were supplied by Hysol-Grafil Ltd. The following table shows the basic properties of the fibres.

Table 1: Properties of Fibres by Hysol-Grafil Ltd

Fibre properties	Carbon Fibre	Glass Fibre
Youngs Modulus(Gpa)	280	72
UTS(Mpa)	2700	3400
Density (gcm ⁻³)	2.00	2.54

Ceramic (alumina AD-29 AL₂O₃)

The high purity alumina ceramic (ADS-96R PERCPS-STD-49) was supplied by Coors Ceramic Wales Ltd, Wales, in two different thicknesses of 0.76 and 1.52 mm discs which were used as layers inside the composite target. The physical and mechanical properties of the AD-96 ceramic discs may be found in literature.

EXPERIMENTAL EQUIPMENT

Toolings, Equipment And Apparatus For Powder Compaction

The present investigation necessitated the fabrication of a special punch and die set in order to carry out compaction work of powder and powder reinforced material so as to prepare disc type target specimens.

The detailed explanation of the fundamental and basic requirements considered in designing the compaction tools can be found from the Powder Metallurgy Equipment Manual[3] and other references[4,5].

Ballistic Impact Test Rig

Figure 1 shows a diagram of the ballistic impact test rig which was designed and fabricated for the purpose of performing the perforation tests. Basically, the ballistic rig consisted of a rigid channel-shaped base on which a gun barrel of 9.65mm nominal bore diameter and 84 cm length was mounted. The gun was a Tornado type and was fixed to one end of the gun barrel. On the other end of the gun barrel a specially designed unit for measuring the projectile velocity was fixed. In the line of fire of the projectile was a containment box, in front of which was fixed a specially designed sub-rig. The sub-rig was used to hold both the target plate and the unit for measuring the residual velocity of the projectile. In order to have a complete assessment of the deformation and the perforation process, it was felt important to collect both the projectile and the plug if it formed from the target plate after the impact, without inflicting further physical damage.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of ballistic rig

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Preparation Of The Target Specimens

i) Filling of the die with a predetermined weight of metal powder or mixed metal powder and fibre content. In the target specimens where ceramic discs as layers were used, they were either put before or after the fibre layer depending on the devised arrangements.; ii) Pressing the powder or the composite to the required pressure: and, iii) Ejection.

During pressing, the pressure was applied gradually and was maintained for at least 60 seconds. The maximum applied pressure was about 40 kgf/mm²

Fabricating Specimens In Each Group

The specimens were produced according to the individual requirement of the various tests carried out in the present study. They were categorized in 4 groups. (see Table 2).

Table 2. Comparison between the experimental results of perforation tests on 9mm thick fibre reinforced S.A.P. targets.

Group	Target No	kind of Fibre and its Condition	% of Fibre	Experimental Results		
				initlal Velocity W _i m/sec	Final Velocity W _f m/sec	Duration Time t _f (μsec)
2(a)	C.R.10	Carbon	0.5	501	422.5	38.1
	C.R.11		1	499	401	38.9
	C.R.12	Randomly mix	2	488	363	39
	C.R.13		3	509	331	40.6
	C.R.14		4	498	336	38
3(a)	G.R.15	Glass fibre	0.5	496	416	37
	G.R.16		1	494	387	46.3
	G.R.17	Randomly mix	2	491	358	71
	G.R.18		3	502	348	57.2
	G.R.19		4	502	359	55.7
2(b)	C.P.20	Carbon fibre	0.5	503	412	30.7
	C.P.21		1	501	391	44.5
	C.P.22	in plane	2	500	360	45.6
	C.P.23		3	505	353	50.3
	C.P.24		4	499	369	50.9
3(b)	G.P.25	Glass fibre	0.5	500	420	44
	G.P.26		1	511	414	44.2
	G.P.27	in plane	2	502	381	40.7
	G.P.28		3	505	384	48.1
	G.P.29		4	498	393	52.3

Ballistic Test Procedure

Flat-ended cylindrical mild steel bullets (9.5mm diameter and 8.2g in weight) were used to perforate the various composite targets made of compacted powder, reinforced with layers of either ceramic or carbon and glass fibre reinforcements. An approximately constant initial velocity (500ms⁻¹ (+10)) was used for each of the tests. During each experiment, the initial and final velocities of the bullet was measured and recorded using the basic setup explained earlier.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figures 2 and 3 show the dependence of the relative velocity drop on the variation of the percentage of glass or carbon fibres randomly mixed or placed as a layer in the aluminium powder. Each set of target was tested in duplicate. The mean values of the results are shown as thick lines in Figs. 2 and 3.

The variation in the relative velocity drop was also in the same sense when the carbon fibres were inserted in the form of layers up to 3 percent of carbon fibre addition. In this case, see Fig. 3, the relative velocity drop increased from 18 to 30 percent for the increase in the addition of carbon fibres from 0.5 to 3 percent and started to reduce to 26 percent for a 4 percent addition of carbon fibres by volume.

From Fig. 2 it is seen that for SAP target with randomly mixed carbon fibres, the rate of increase in the relative drop increases from 15 to 33 percent when the addition of carbon fibres increases from 0.5 to 4 percent.

Figure 2. Experimental velocity drop of projectiles perforating C.S.A.P. targets mixed with glass or carbon fibres.

In the case of reinforcements of the SAP compacts with the glass fibres, the results of ballistic performance are also shown plotted in Figs. 2 and 3. It was observed that the fibre glass reinforcements also increases the ability of each of the targets to reduce the projectiles residual velocity. However, the rate of increase is less than when the carbon fibres of the same percentage by volume were used as reinforcements. Studying carefully the failure mechanism in the perforated. S. A. P. targets, reinforced with different percentage of carbon fibres randomly mixed, it was observed that in each case the main deformation mode was by plugging. The above mechanism is in combination with some peeling off of the material at the back of the target, in some cases near to the exit hole. From a careful observation of the shapes of the perforated carbon fibre reinforced targets it was further observed that as the percentage of the carbon fibre in the target increased, the amount of material which peeled off from the back of the perforated targets also increased. This is most probably due to the increased binding of more and more powder particles with the fibres. The presence of these added fibres transmits extra kinetic energy to the powder particles situated far from the impact point which helps to absorb more of the projectile's energy and hence reduces its velocity. From the observation made on the perforated SAP targets having a different percentage of glass fibres in each, it was found that appearance and the modes of

Figure 3. Experimental velocity drop of projectiles perforating C.S.A.P. targets with glass or carbon fibres as a layer.

failure in these specimens is similar to those observed in the case of specimens reinforced with carbon fibres mixed in a random manner in each case.

The SAP targets with varying percentages of carbon fibres reinforcements, where the fibres were inserted as a layer in the middle of the target and those specimens which had a layer of glass fibres of varying percentages were also examined. From a careful observation of the deformed targets, it was noticed that the targets which had a low content of fibres, ie. 0.5%, plugging was the mode of deformation. In all the pierced targets, two separate plugs in each of the specimens were produced. As the carbon fibre content increased, the mode of deformation changed to a combination of plugging and petalling. A plug was obtained from the material in the front of the carbon fibre and petals were formed from the material at the back of the fibre layer. An explanation of this behaviour is the increased overall resistance offered by the layer of carbon fibres which causes the applied load to be spread over a large area on to the back of the composite target instead of it being localised as in a single material. Thus, the layer of fibres acted similar to a net trying to arrest the projectile. It was also observed that there was more symmetry in the formation of these petals in the case of targets which had higher percentages of carbon fibres. This also suggested that, in the case of higher fibre content targets, a more uniform distribution of load around the projectile was generated. Generally speaking, for both classes of fibre reinforced targets, when fibres were high, more delamination of the material from the area in the front and at the back of the fibre layer was observed.

In general, targets with a mixed fibre reinforcement have better ballistic resistance than the targets with fibre reinforcement as layer if the fibre content is high, ie. 3 to 4 percent. This is, of course, the opposite in the case of low fibre content targets.

BALLISTIC PERFORATION OF SAP TARGETS CONTAINING CERAMIC LAYERS

Fig. 4 shows the variation in relative drop of velocity, plotted with variation of the percentage depth of ceramic layer as observed during the ballistic penetration of SAP targets with total thickness, h , of 9 to 10mm containing a ceramic layer which was inserted inside each of these at positions of $0.2h$, $0.4h$, $0.5h$ and $0.8h$ as measured from the firing side. From the results shown in Fig. 4, it may be seen that the best ballistic performance was achieved by the target where the ceramic layer was placed nearest to

the firing side of the target, ie. at 0.2h, and not deep inside it. For the specified targets tested, the results showed that the decrease in the percentage of the velocity drop was generally not high, ie. 2%, when the ceramic is placed up to 0.5h, but it follows a relatively sharp decrease after that, ie. 8% . This may be due to stress wave propagation

Figure 4. Experimental velocity drop of projectiles perforating C.S.A.P. targets with a layer of ceramic at different depth from the firing side of the target.

in the target and also the amount and thickness of the back-up material behind the ceramic layer. When the ceramic layer is nearer to the impact face, it has a larger amount of SAP material in the back for support. In this case, it absorbs more of the projectile's energy at the very beginning of the perforation process due to its high compressive strength. But if the ceramic layer was near to the back surface of the target, impact energy absorbed is less because firstly there is only a small amount of SAP material at its back, and secondly since the waves reach the ceramic layer sooner than the projectile hits it and thus causes the ceramic layer to be shattered before the projectile reaches it. Therefore, placing the ceramic layer near to the back surface does not have a substantial beneficial effect on the ballistic performance of the target.

Another interesting observation was also made by comparing the shattered and broken pieces of the ceramic layers after impact from the different target specimens. From the examination of the broken ceramic pieces obtained from two extreme situations, it may be seen that when the ceramic layer was nearest to the firing side, the broken pieces are smaller than the broken pieces when the ceramic layer was placed very far from the firing side. This confirms the observation that placing the ceramic layer nearer to the firing side absorbs more of the impact energy of the bullet and thus decreases the residual velocity of the bullet by a larger amount. When the ceramic pieces become smaller, which means more cracks that involves more energy absorption by the ceramic layer due to the formation of the cracks which in turn results in greater reduction in the bullet's velocity.

CONCLUSIONS

From a detailed experimental investigation made into the ballistic penetration of a combination of SAP and glass / carbon fibres targets., and targets made from a composite of SAP and of ceramic layer; the following conclusions can be made:

1. That, in general, the ballistic resistance of the SAP target increases with the addition of glass or carbon fibres to it. This may either be in the randomly mixed form, mixed with powder before compacton, or placed as a layer at the middle of the target. In general, targets with distributed (mix) fibre reinforcement have better ballistic resistance than the targets with fibre reinforcement as layers if the fibre content is high, ie. 3 to 4 percent. This is, of course, opposite in the case of low fibre content targets. In both cases, whether these fibres are randomly mixed or inserted in the form of a layer, in both kinds of fibres the best performance was achieved in specimens when the fibre content was 3 percent by volume of that target [6].

2. That the ballistic resistance of the SAP target also increases when it is reinforced with a layer of ceramic disc placed within the compact. The best ballistic performance was achieved by placing the ceramic layer rather nearer to the firing side than when it was placed towards the back of the target.

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